

2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldehyde Chelates of Some* Rare Earths and Some Ligand Exchange Reactions

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Tris(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato)neodymium(III), -praseodymium(III), -samarium(III), cerium(III) and lanthanum(III) have been synthesised as yellowish green compounds. The infrared spectra and magnetic susceptibility data as well as some ligand exchange reactions of these complexes have been discussed.

THIS communication deals with the isolation of tris(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato)neodymium(III), -praseodymium(III), -samarium(III), -cerium(III) and -lanthanum(III). Infrared spectra and magnetic susceptibility data on these complexes have been presented and discussed. Some ligand exchange reactions of these complexes as well as other metal complexes of the above ligand with ethylenediamine-tetraacetic acid (EDTA) and 1,3-diamino-2-hydroxypropanol N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (HPTA) have also been reported.

Experimental

The hydrated nitrates of rare earth metals used were of 99.9% purity (obtained from Bhabha Atomic Research Center, Bombay). 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde was prepared as described in the literature¹ and was recrystallized twice from alcohol. 1,3-Diamino-2-propanol N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid was also prepared by the reported procedure². Other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

The general method followed for the preparation of the rare earth chelates is as follows:

To a magnetically stirred solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (0.015 mole) in ethyl alcohol (150 ml.),

a solution of rare earth metal nitrate (0.005 mole) in 80% ethyl alcohol (25 ml.) was slowly added. Dilute ammonia (1:20) was then added dropwise to this mixture until a flocculent yellowish-green precipitate was formed. The stirring was continued for a further period of about 8 hrs. The product was collected on a filter, under suction, washed with hot alcohol and dried first in the air and later under vacuum. The yields and the analyses of the products are given in Table I.

Complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with Copper(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), palladium(II), uranium(VI) and molybdenum(VI), were prepared by the known procedures³⁻⁵ and their purity was checked by the analysis.

Ligand replacement reactions

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato metal chelate (0.01 mole) was added to a suspension of EDTA or HPTA (0.01 mole) in water (150 ml) and the mixture was kept for one hour, on a boiling water bath. The solution was cooled and the separated 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde was removed using chloroform as a solvent. The aqueous solution was concentrated on a water bath to about one third its original volume

TABLE I. ANALYSES, YIELDS AND THE μ_{eff} VALUES OF 2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALDEHYDE CHELATES OF RARE EARTHS

Complex	Composition	Yield %	Analyses						μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			Found %			Required %			
			C	H	Metal	C	H	Metal	
La(NA) ₃	LaC ₃₃ H ₂₁ O ₆	71	60.12	3.47	21.50	60.75	3.25	21.29	—
Ce(NA) ₃	CeC ₃₃ H ₂₁ O ₆	73	59.92	4.13	21.27	60.63	3.24	21.43	—
Pr(NA) ₃	PrC ₃₃ H ₂₁ O ₆	69	60.32	3.33	21.61	60.56	3.23	21.53	3.31
Nd(NA) ₃	NdC ₃₃ H ₂₁ O ₆	76	60.36	3.30	21.79	60.24	3.22	21.94	3.55
Sm(NA) ₃	SmC ₃₃ H ₂₁ O ₆	75	59.22	3.57	22.58	59.69	3.19	22.64	1.53

(NA⁻ represents anion of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde).

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and was allowed to cool. The crystals obtained were separated by filtration and from the filtrate

more product was recovered by further concentration. The product was dried under vacuum.

From the chloroform extract, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde was recovered in every case almost in quantitative yield by concentration and then by crystallization.

Infrared spectra of the compounds in Nujol mull were recorded on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer, Model 137E, using sodium chloride prism. Magnetic measurements were done by the Faraday method, calibrating the apparatus with mercury(II) thiocyanatocobaltate.

Results and Discussion

The yellowish-green rare earth chelates of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde are insoluble in water and common organic solvents. They are stable upto 200° and decompose without melting thereafter yielding the oxide in the range 500°-600°.

The broad band present in the ligand spectrum at 3450 cm^{-1} attributed to the hydroxyl group, is absent in the spectra of the rare earth complexes. The strong band at 1650 cm^{-1} and at 1600 cm^{-1} are due to C=O and C=C stretching vibrations. However, on chelation of the ligand with rare earth metals, there is no shift in the carbonyl frequency, although a decrease in the carbonyl frequency on chelation with some transition metals is reported. Also in the spectra of the rare earth chelates of salicylaldehyde⁶ and acetoacetanilide⁷ a shift in the carbonyl frequency (on chelation) is not observed.

Tris (2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) La(III) has been found to be diamagnetic. The magnetic moments (spin-free values, Table 1) observed for the other rare earth chelates are in good agreement with the values reported for typical lanthanide sulphates⁸. These values show that the lanthanide ion acts, approximately as free ion, as far as the *f*-electrons are concerned.

The above rare earth chelates of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have been found to undergo replacement reactions with stronger chelating ligand, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). They yielded on treatment with EDTA in aqueous solution the corresponding EDTA chelates in pure form. Synthesis of metal-EDTA complexes by ligand replacement is interesting as this method precludes anion penetration possibilities. The successful ligand replacement with EDTA in the case of the above rare earth chelates led us to similar attempts with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde chelates of other metals. We successfully prepared by this method the EDTA chelates of copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II), palladium(II), molybdenum(VI) and uranium(VI). We also isolated by this method the copper(II) and cobalt(II) chelates of HPTA.

Infrared spectra of the EDTA chelates isolated in the above manner were found to be identical with the reported spectra.

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References

1. Organic Syntheses, Collect. Vol. 3, Ed., E. C. Horning, 1955, p. 463.
2. V. SPRINGER, J. MAJER and B. KOPECKA, *Chem. Zvests.*, 1967, **21**, 481. *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, **68**, 354 32y.
3. V. I. KUMOV, Z. A. BITOVY and A. S. PESIS, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1958, **3**, 1181.
4. D. P. GRADDON and G. M. MOCKLER, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1968, **21**, 617, 1487 and 1769.
5. J. G. LARA, *Bol. Inst. Quim. Univ. Nacl. Auton. Mex.*, 1964, **16**, 25. *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **63**, 2610g.
6. R. G. CHARLES, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 2298.
7. A. P. BUDHKAR, P. UMAPATHY and D. N. SEN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 378.
8. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Techniques of Inorganic Chemistry*, Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1965, **4**, 137.